

Adherence to Diabetes Self-care Behaviours and Associated Factors amongst Adults with Type 2 Diabetes in an Urban Setting in Cameroon

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is currently a major global public health burden associated with acute and chronic complications. Adherence to some diabetes self-care behaviours slows the progression of short-term and long-term adverse cardiovascular outcomes. The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of adherence to some domains of diabetes self-care behaviours and to identify the factors associated with adherence amongst adults living with type 2 diabetes in the Bamenda III health district of the North West Region of Cameroon. **Methods:** A community-based cross-sectional study involving 162 adults living with type 2 diabetes (mean age 57.1± 9.6 years) living in the Bamenda III health district in the North West Region of Cameroon using a convenient random sampling technique. Anthropometric and diabetes related measurements were carried out following standard procedures. Adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours was assessed using a self-administered structured questionnaire. Logistic regression analysis was used to identify the predictors of diabetes self-care behaviours. **Results:** The overall prevalence of diabetes self-care adherence in the study population was 36.4%. In addition, we observed that there was a significantly ($p=0.002$) higher mean FBS amongst participants with poor dietary adherence compared to those with good dietary (175.4mg/dl vs 136.8 mg/dl) respectively. Bivariate analysis revealed being 67 years and older (OR 5.3) and diabetes duration of more than 5 years (OR 4.6) were significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. Multivariate analysis indicated that being older than 67 years (OR 4.8, 95% CI, 1.9 – 14.8) was an

independent predictor for adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. **Conclusion:** This study has shown a poor overall adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours amongst adults living with type 2 diabetes in our setting. In addition, being older than 67 years was an independent predictor of good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. There is need for an integrated approach in the management of T2DM involving treatment as well as health education that will improve on the health and quality of life of the patients. **Keywords:** *Type 2 diabetes, adherence, self-care, adults, North West Region, Cameroon*

1.0. Background

Diabetes mellitus is a complex multifactorial disorder characterized mainly by hyperglycaemia resulting from the defects in the action of insulin and/or the secretion of insulin. According to the International Diabetes Federation [1], diabetes has been described as one of the fastest growing global public health emergencies of the 21st century, affecting more than half a billion people worldwide. Globally, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) accounts for about 90-95% of all the cases of diabetes. Moreover, more than 80% of people living with diabetes reside in low-and-middle-income countries [1, 2, 3] and it is associated with high morbidity and mortality rates [3, 4, 5]. According to the American Diabetes Association [6], the management of diabetes involves continuous medical care and patient self-management education to prevent acute and long-term complications. Evidence has shown that adherence to diabetes self-care behaviour is an important aspect of diabetes management and it helps improve on the quality of life of patients and slows the progression of adverse cardiovascular outcomes in type 2 diabetes patients [7, 8, 9]. However, poor adherence to diabetes self-care practices increases the risk of acute and chronic complications [10, 11].

Adherence to the diabetes self-care management practices involves a lifestyle modification including; regular physical activity, following a healthy diet plan, medication compliance, diabetic foot care and self-monitoring of blood glucose (BGM) [12, 13]. Adherence to self-care management practices aims at lowering the glycosylated haemoglobin of the patients. Nevertheless, poor management of T2DM affects the quality of life of patients resulting in adverse health outcomes [14]. Notwithstanding, there is a wide variation in the self-care adherence rates amongst adults living with T2DM from one country to another due to individual factors (such as gender, age, occupation, level of education and marital status),

cultural factors and health system factors. For example, adherence to diabetes self-care amongst adult type 2 diabetics ranges from 32.5% to 63.7% in India [15], Nepal [16], Brazil [17], Nigeria [18] and Ethiopia [19]. In addition, inter-country variation has been observed in some reports. For instance, in Ethiopia, diabetes self-care adherence rates vary from 42.7% to 63.6% in Addis Abba [20], Western Ethiopia [21, 22] and Southeast Ethiopia [23, 24].

Studies have demonstrated that adherence rates to diabetes self-care behaviours amongst adults in the less developed nations is poor [8, 15, 22]. For instance, a study in Ethiopia reported that only 42.7% of the study participants had good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours [22]. Similarly, a study by Burman *et al.*[15] in India reported that 32.5% of type 2 diabetic patients had good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. Another report by Portela *et al.* [8] in Brazil found that adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours was greater for medications (91.5%) but lower with BGM (25.6%), physical activity (22.6%) and diet (42.2%). In addition, Agidew *et al.*[23] in southern Ethiopia reported that a significant number of patients living with diabetes had poor adherence to diabetes self-care practices with poor adherence found in BGM, diet and physical activity. Finally, another report by Degefa *et al.*[(17] in Brazil also found that 52.2% of T2DM patients did not adhere to the prescribed diabetes self-care behaviours.

Nonetheless, evidence has demonstrated that sociodemographic variables such as age, gender, family history of DM and diabetes duration of the patient are associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours amongst adults with T2DM; with younger age, longer diabetes duration and family history of diabetes positively influencing diabetes self-care behaviours in patients [8, 19, 24]. For instance, a report by Kassa *et al.* [24] aimed at assessing diabetes self-care practices amongst 301 adults with T2DM in South East Ethiopia found that younger age; longer diabetes duration and family history of DM were significantly associated with good diabetes self-care behaviours. Another study carried out in northeastern Ethiopia also found that younger age was positively associated with diabetes self-care practices [19]. Similarly, Portela *et al.* [8] in Brazil also found younger age to be significantly associated with good diabetes self-care behaviours amongst T2DM patients.

In addition, reports have shown that having a glucometer at home positively increased adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours [22, 24]. However, some studies have shown that level of education was positively associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours

with those who have attained university education more likely to have good adherence to diabetes self-care practices compared to those with no formal education [25, 26, 27].

In Cameroon, there is limited data on the prevalence of good adherence towards diabetes self-care practices and the factors associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours amongst adults living with type 2 diabetes. Understanding the predictors of adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours in this study population will provide valuable information that will contribute in guiding policymakers in bridging the information gap on diabetes self-care for patients and thus minimizing the burden of the disease on patients.

This study therefore set out to determine the prevalence of adherence to some domains of diabetes self-care behaviours and to identify the factors associated with adherence amongst adults living with type 2 diabetes in the Bamenda III health district of the North West Region of Cameroon.

2.0. Materials and methods

2.1. Study participants

This study was a community-based cross-sectional study carried out in 2022 involving 162 adults living with type 2 diabetes (mean age 57.1 ± 9.6 years) living in the Bamenda III health district in the North West Region of Cameroon using a convenient random sampling technique. The selection of participants was based on the fact that they had been diagnosed for type 2 diabetes according to the WHO criteria of 1999 [28] in a hospital. However, participants with cognitive problems were excluded.

2.2. Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of The University of Bamenda (Ref N° 2022/0423H/UBa/IRB). Administrative clearance was gotten from the Regional Delegation of Public Health of the North West Region (Ref N° 203/ATT/NWR/RDPH/BRIGAD). Written informed consent was obtained from all the quarter heads and study participants before any data collection procedure started. A written consent that explained the purpose of the study was distributed to the study participants. In addition, the nurses explained the purpose of the study before any data collection and those who consented to the study were asked to sign the consent form..

2.2.Data collection

Anthropometry and blood glycaemia (Fasting Blood sugar)

Data for this study was collected at home in the early hours of the morning (between 7am and 9am) in order for participant to be in a fasting state. Height and weight were measured ensuring all standard procedures were respected by well trained nurses recruited to assist in the data collection process. Height was measured without any shoes using a portable stadiometer (Seca 213, Germany) to the nearest 0.1cm, while a digital scale (Omron BF511, Japan) was used for the measurement of body weight to the nearest 0.1kg. Body mass index (BMI) for each patient was then calculated as weight (kg)/ height (cm)² [29].

Fasting blood sugar was measured using an Accu-Chek Active Blood Glucose monitoring system (Germany). Glycaemic control was assessed using fasting blood sugar (FBS) as a proxy with good glycaemic control considered as FBS measurement between 70 and 126mg/dl [6, 30]

Adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours was assessed using a self-administered structured questionnaire, which was adapted from the Summary of Diabetes Self-Care Activities (SDSCA) questionnaire by Toobert *et al.* [31]. The SDSCA scale has been validated and good to be used amongst adults living with T2DM in Europe and amongst African Americans [31, 32]. The questionnaire was made up of 20 questions and it assessed the self-reported frequency of adhering to four main areas of diabetes self-care. These included eating a healthy diet as well as frequency of consuming fruits and vegetables with a reduction in the consumption of high fatty foods; measuring of blood glucose at least once a day and carrying out moderate-to-rigorous physical activities for at least 30 min/day and taking of prescribed medications in the past 7 days. The greater the number of days reported for a behaviour the better the self-care. The questionnaire was piloted amongst 15 randomly selected adults living with type 2 diabetes in the Bamenda I health district two weeks prior to data collection to ascertain the effectiveness of the questionnaire.

- a) Dietary adherence: patient adherence to diet was assessed using a scoring process of following a low-fat eating plan. A maximum score of 10 was obtained for dietary adherence and a score of less than 7 and ≥ 7 were interpreted as poor and good dietary adherence respectively.

- b) Blood glucose monitoring adherence: this was classified as good for those who measured their blood glucose at least once a day and poor for those who did not measure their blood glucose every day in the past 7 days respectively.
- c) Physical activity adherence was graded as good for patients who carried out moderate-to-rigorous exercises for 30mins/day for at least 3 days in the last one-week and poor for those who did not exercise or exercised for less than 30 minutes/day during the last 7 days.
- d) Medication adherence was rated as good for those who took their prescribed medications regularly and/or rarely missed a dose of their medications and poor for those who always forgot to take their medications.
- e) Overall adherence to the diabetes self-care behaviours was assessed using an overall score of 20 for all the 4 domains of adherence. Any patient with an overall score of 15 and above and less than 15 in all 4 domains were interpreted as good and poor respectively.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS for Windows version 23.0. Continuous variables were checked for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test. Patients' sociodemographic characteristics, diabetes related and treatment characteristics were summarized using frequency distribution tables and charts. Association between categorical variables was assessed using Chi square test. Means of clinical and biochemical characteristics of the study participants was assessed using an independent student t-test and ANOVA as appropriate. Binary logistic regression analysis was done to identify the predictors of diabetes self-care behaviours followed by multiple logistic regression to identify independent predictors of diabetes self-care practices in the study population. All measures of association were presented as odds ratios with their 95% confidence interval. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3.0. Results

3.1. Descriptive characteristics of the study participants

Table 1 shows the descriptive characteristics of the study participants according to family history of diabetes. This study involved 162 adults living with type 2 diabetes (mean age 57.1 ± 9.6 years). More than two-thirds (67.9%) of the study participants were females, with 56.8% of them being in the age group 51 – 66 years. We found that 48.8% had a family history of diabetes, 80.2% were overweight/obese and 46.3% had been living with diabetes for 2 – 5

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years. With respect to family history of diabetes mellitus (DM) , we found that 32.6% of the study population were in the age group 30 – 50 years compared to 22.2.% who were ≥ 67 years and the difference was significant ($X^2 = 21.530, p < 0.001$). In addition, this study found that 78.3% of the study participants with a family history of DM had attained university compared to 40.5% who had attained only primary education and this difference was significant ($X^2 = 10.504, p = 0.005$). Moreover, a higher proportion of patients with a family history of DM had been living with diabetes for less than 2 years compared to those with a diabetes duration of more than 5 years (87.5% vs 55.7% respectively) and this difference was statistically significant ($X^2 = 10.857, p = 0.004$). Again, a higher proportion of the BMI normal weight study participants (59.4%) had a family history of DM compared to their BMI-obese counterparts (47.2%). However, these difference was not significant ($X^2 = 1.870, p = 0.393$).

3.2. Diabetes related and treatment characteristics of the study participants

Table 2 shows the diabetes related and treatment characteristics of the study participants according to family history of diabetes. The prevalence of poor glycaemic control amongst the study participants as measured by FBS was 54.3% with a higher proportion of poor glycaemic control amongst patients with no family history of DM compared to those with a family history of diabetes (59.0% vs 41.0% respectively). However, this difference was not significant ($X^2 = 1.557, p = 0.214$). In addition, a higher proportion (55.8%) of males has poor glycaemic control compared to their female counterparts (50.0%) and it was not significant ($p = 0.493$). Moreover, a higher proportion (66.0%) of the study participants with a family history of DM had a glucometer compared to those with no family history of DM (34.0%) and this difference was significant ($X^2 = 7.822, p = 0.005$). In this present study, no significant difference ($X^2 = 2.610, p = 0.271$) was observed in physical activity duration between patients with a family history of DM and those without a family history of DM. Again, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed in the SBP and DBP amongst type 2 diabetic patients with a family history of DM and those without a family history. Notwithstanding, there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) observed with respect to the number of medication types currently used and cost of medication between those with a family history and those without a family history of DM. Nonetheless, all the study participants reported that the hospital pharmacy was the main source of purchase for medications. Furthermore, for BGM and dietary adherence, a significant

difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed amongst type 2 diabetics with a family history of DM and those without a family history of DM, a finding not observed with physical activity adherence.

Table 1: Descriptive characteristics of the study participants according to family history of diabetes (N= 162)

Variable	Whole sample (N=162)	Family History of diabetes		χ^2	p-value
		Yes (N=79) n (%)	No (N= 83) n (%)		
Age (years)				21.520	<0.001
30 – 50	43	14(32.6)	29(67.4)		
51 – 66	92	59(64.1)	33(35.9)		
≥ 67	27	6(22.2)	21(77.8)		
Gender				0.792	0.374
Male	52	28(53.8)	24(46.2)		
Female	110	51(46.4)	59(53.6)		
Level of education				10.504	0.005
Primary	74	30(40.5)	44(59.5)		
Secondary/ High school	65	31(47.7)	34(52.3)		
University	23	18(78.3)	5(21.7)		
Marital status				0.065	0.799
Married	132	65(49.2)	67(50.8)		
Widow/widower	30	14(46.7)	16(53.3)		
Occupation				5.720	0.017
Farming	58	22(37.9)	36(62.1)		
Business	44	21(47.7)	23(52.3)		
Civil servant	60	36(60.0)	24(40.0)		
Religion				1.343	0.246
Christian	161	79(49.1)	82(50.9)		
Muslim	1	0(0.0)	1(100)		
Diabetes duration (years)				10.857	0.004
< 2	8	7(87.5)	1(12.5)		
2 – 5	75	28(37.3)	47(62.7)		
>5	79	44(55.7)	35(44.3)		
BMI Categories (kg/m ²)				1.870	0.393
Normal weight	32	19(59.4)	13(40.6)		
Overweight	58	26(44.8)	32(55.2)		
Obesity	72	34(47.2)	38(52.8)		

BMI; Body mass index

Table 2: Diabetes related and treatment characteristics of the study participants (N=162)

Variable	Whole sample (N=162)	Family History of diabetes		X ²	p*-value
		Yes [n (%)]	No [n (%)]		
Have a glucometer at home				7.832	0.005
Yes	47	31(66.0)	16(34.0)		
No	115	48(41.7)	67(58.3)		
Fasting blood sugar (mg/dl)				1.525	0.217
≤ 126	74	40(54.1)	34(45.9)		
>126	88	39(44.3)	49(55.7)		
BGM adherence				7.927	0.009
Good	47	31(66.0)	16(34.0)		
Poor	115	48(41.7)	67(58.3)		
Dietary adherence				7.541	0.006
Good	106	60(56.6)	46(43.4)		
Poor	56	19(33.9)	37(66.1)		
Physical activity adherence				0.179	0.672
Good	95	45(47.4)	50(52.6)		
Poor	67	34(50.7)	33(49.3)		
Medication adherence				1.572	0.210
Good	80	43(53.8)	37(46.2)		
Poor	82	36(43.9)	46(56.1)		
Number of medication types currently used				8.590	0.014
Stopped medications	10	1(10.0)	9(90.0)		
One type	100	47(47.0)	53(53.0)		
Two types	52	31(59.6)	21(40.4)		
Cost of medications (Easy to buy)				15.565	<0.001
Yes	65	44(67.7)	21(32.3)		
No	97	35(36.1)	62(63.9)		
Insulin dose				2.432	0.296
Not on insulin	149	71(47.7)	78(52.3)		
Once a day	5	2(40.0)	3(60.0)		
Twice daily	8	6(75.0)	2(25.0)		
Physical activity duration				2.610	0.271
30 minutes 3 days/week	75	39(52.0)	36(48.0)		
< 30 minutes/day	63	26(41.3)	37(58.7)		
Never	24	14(58.3)	10(41.7)		
Diabetes complications				0.026	0.872
Yes	118	58(49.2)	60(50.8)		
No	44	21(47.7)	23(52.3)		
Systolic Blood pressure (mmHg)				2.710	0.258
< 120	29	18(62.1)	11(37.9)		
120 – 129	33	14(42.4)	19(57.6)		
≥ 130	100	47(47.0)	53(53.0)		
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)				1.698	0.428
< 80	50	25(50.0)	25(50.0)		
80 – 89	63	27(42.9)	36(57.1)		
≥90	49	27(55.1)	22(44.9)		

CI: Confidence interval; BGM: Blood glucose monitoring

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3.3. Mean clinical and biochemical characteristics of the study participants

Table 3 shows the mean clinical and biochemical characteristics of the study participants by gender. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the mean age, weight, systolic BP, diastolic BP and diabetes duration amongst study participants according to gender. Nonetheless, participants 51 – 66 years had on average a significantly ($p= 0.039$) higher mean weight compared to those ≥ 67 years (90.3kg vs 72.1kg) respectively. Males had a higher mean fasting blood sugar (151.2mg/dl) compared to females (149.6mg/dl), however, this was not significant ($p =0.882$). Moreover, there was a significant difference ($p =0.019$) in the mean FBS by age with those 30 – 50 years (172.9mg/dl) having a higher mean FBS compared to those ≥ 67 years (142.1mg/dl). In addition, males were significantly ($p <0.001$) taller (169.5cm) than to females (160.4 cm). On the contrary, females had a significantly ($p <0.001$) higher mean BMI (30.8 kg/m²) compared to males (26.7 kg/m²).

Table 3: Mean clinical and biochemical characteristics of the study participants by gender (N=162)

Variable	Whole sample n=162 Mean (95% CI)	Males (n=52) Mean (95% CI)	Females (n=110) Mean (95% CI)	<i>p</i> *-value
Age (years)	57.1 (55.6 – 58.6)	57.3 (54.7 – 59.9)	57.0 (55.1 – 58.9)	0.887
Height (cm)	163.3 (162.2 – 164.4)	169.5 (167.4 – 171.6)	160.4 (159.4 – 161.4)	<0.001
Weight (kg)	78.5 (76.2 – 80.8)	76.7 (72.9 – 80.5)	79.4 (76.5 – 82.3)	0.291
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.5 (28.6 – 30.4)	26.7 (25.5 – 27.9)	30.8 (29.7 – 31.9)	<0.001
Diabetes duration (years)	6.5 (5.9 – 7.1)	6.4 (5.3 – 7.5)	6.5 (5.7 – 7.2)	0.805
FBS (mg/dl)	150.1 (140.4 – 159.8)	151.2 (135.8 – 166.6)	149.6 (137.1 – 162.1)	0.882
SBP (mmHg)	136.3 (133.6 – 139.0)	134.9 (130.1 – 139.7)	136.9 (133.5 – 140.3)	0.488
DBP (mmHg)	85.6 (83.9 – 87.3)	85.7 (83.1 – 88.3)	85.6 (83.4 – 87.6)	0.939

*Calculated using Independent student t-test; SBP: Systolic blood pressure; DBP: Diastolic blood pressure; BMI: Body mass index; FBS: Fasting blood sugar

3.4. Adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours in the study population

This study found that the overall prevalence of good adherence to the diabetes self-care behaviours amongst of the study participants was 36.4%. We also observed that less than half of the study participants had good BGM (29.0%), medication (49.5%) and physical activity (46.3%) respectively, while 65.4% had good dietary adherence. Figure 1 shows the diabetes self-care adherence ratings reported by the study participants.

Figure 1: Diabetes self-care adherence ratings reported by the study population

With respect to glycaemic control, we observed that there was a significantly ($p= 0.002$) higher mean FBS amongst participants with poor dietary adherence compared to those with good dietary (175.4mg/dl vs 136.8 mg/dl) respectively. In contrast, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed in the mean FBS with respect to BGM, physical activity and medication adherence. Table 4 shows the differences in diabetes self-care adherence and glycaemic control in the study population.

Table 4: Differences in diabetes self-care adherence and glycaemic control (N=162)

Self-care adherence	Fasting blood sugar Mean (95% CI)				<i>p</i> -value*
	Good		Poor		
Diet	136.8	(129.9 – 143.7)	175.4	(162.7 – 188.1)	0.002
BGM	154.8	(143.8 – 165.8)	148.2	(139.1 – 157.3)	0.544
Physical activity	148.5	(135.4 – 161.6)	151.5	(137.2 – 165.8)	0.762
Medication	142.1	(133.9 – 150.3)	157.9	(147.0 - 168.8)	0.105

*Calculated using independent student *t*-test

3.5. Predictors of adherence to diabetes self-care practices in the study population

Table 5 below indicated being 67 years and older (OR 5.3, 95% CI, 1.1 – 10.8) and diabetes duration of more than 5 years (OR 4.6, 95% CI, 1.2 – 13.9) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. While, being female (OR 0.7, 95% CI, 0.30 – 1.4) and good adherence to BGM (OR 1.1, 95% CI, 0.60 – 2.3) were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. In addition, good adherence to medication intake (OR 1.2, 95% CI, 0.6 – 2.3) and a physical activity duration of 30 minutes/day (OR 0.8, 95% CI, 0.3 – 2.0) were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours.

On multivariate analysis, being older than 67 years (OR 4.8, 95% CI, 1.9 – 14.8) was an independent predictor for adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours ($p = 0.037$).

4.0. Discussion

Adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours is an important aspect in the management of T2DM given that it helps in improving on the quality of life of patients and it slows the progression of adverse cardiovascular outcomes [7, 8, 9]. However, the adherence to these diabetes self-care behaviours amongst type 2 diabetics remains very challenging even to the most motivated individuals. Notwithstanding, very little attention has been focused on the adherence of diabetes self-care behaviours amongst patients living with type 2 diabetes in the management of T2DM in our setting. Our study therefore set out to determine the proportion of adults living with type 2 diabetes adhering to some specific domains of diabetes self-care behaviours and to identify the factors associated with adherence to these domains of diabetes self-care behaviours

Table 5: Predictors of adherence to diabetes self-care practices in the study population (univariate and multivariate analysis)

Variable	Bivariate				Multivariate		
	N	OR	95% CI	p-value	OR	95% CI	p-value
Age categories (years)							
≥ 67	27	5.3	1.1 – 10.8	0.021	4.8	1.9 – 14.8	0.037
51 – 66	92	2.7	0.6 – 3.8	0.034	1.6	0.6 – 11.4	0.068
35 – 50	43	<i>Ref</i>			<i>Ref</i>		
Gender							
Female	110	0.7	0.3 – 1.4	0.305			
male	52	<i>Ref</i>					
Educational level							
Tertiary	74	0.9	0.3 – 2.4	0.748			
Secondary/ High school	65	0.8	0.3 – 2.3	0.819			
Primary	23	<i>Ref</i>					
Family History of DM							
Yes	79	0.9	0.5 – 1.7	0.801			
Diabetes duration (years)							
>5	79	4.6	1.2 – 13.9	0.048			
2 – 5	75	2.2	1.1 – 4.3	0.025			
<2	8	<i>Ref</i>					
Having a glucometer at home							
Yes	47	1.1	0.6 – 2.3	0.751			
Dietary adherence							
Good	106	1.2	0.4 – 1.7	0.632			
Poor	56	<i>Ref</i>					
BGM adherence							
Good	47	1.1	0.6 – 2.3	0.751			
Poor	115	<i>Ref</i>					
Physical activity duration							
30 minutes	75	0.8	0.3 – 2.0	0.618			
<30minutes/day	63	0.7	0.3 – 1.9	0.560			
Never	24	<i>Ref</i>					
Medication adherence							
Good	80	1.2	0.6 – 2.3	0.543			
Poor	82	<i>Ref</i>					

BGM: Blood glucose monitoring; CI: Confidence interval; OR: Odds ratio

amongst adult type 2 diabetics in the Bamenda III Health District of the North West Region of Cameroon.

This study found that the overall adherence to diabetes self-care practices amongst the study population was poor (36.4%). We also found in the multivariate analysis that, being older than

67 years was an independent predictor for good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviour in our setting.

Our study found that 36.4% of the study population had an overall good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours, a finding similar to that reported in Western Oromia in Ethiopia [21], India [15], Saudi Arabia [34] and Brazil [8] but lower than that reported in Brazil [17] and Ethiopia [19, 23, 24, 25]. Factors such as differences in cultural and lifestyle, non-availability of structured diabetes programs and lack of acceptance of chronic diseases within the society may contribute to these differences. This can also be attributed to lack of awareness on the importance of these self-care practices given that a majority of the study participants had attained only high school.

In this study, we observed that the mean age of the study population was 57.1 ± 9.6 years with more than two-thirds of them being females. These findings are in contrast to those observed by Babazadeh *et al.* [34] in Iran where the authors observed that the mean age of the patients was 46.3yrs and more than half of the study participants were males. We also observed that amongst the study participants 51.9% had poor glycaemic control (measured by FBS), a finding lower than that observed in Jordan [35].

In addition, we observed that 48.8% of the study participants had a family history of diabetes, a finding lower than that reported in Nigeria [18]. We also found that more than 64% of the study population with a family history of DM were within the ages 51 – 66 years and had attained university education. In addition, we observed that participants 51 years and older had a significantly lower FBS compared to those 30 – 50 years. This may reflect better knowledge and awareness of diabetes self-care practices in the older population compared to the younger type 2 diabetics.

Moreover, this study found that 47.2% of study participants with a family history of DM were obese compared to 59.4% who had normal weight. In addition, more than half (53.8%) of the study participants with a family history of DM had good glycaemic control as measured by FBS. Furthermore, more than 55% of the study participants with a family history of DM had good dietary and BGM adherence with more than half of the study population carrying out physical activity for at least 30 minutes/day. The higher low levels of adherence to diet, BGM

and physical activity in our study could be explained by lack of proper education on the benefits of good adherence to the diabetes self-care practices.

This study found that males with T2DM had a higher mean FBS (151.2mg/dl) compared to females (149.6mg/dl). In contrast, females had a higher mean SBP (137.9mmHg) compared to males (134.9mmHg). In this present study, we observed a significant association between glycaemic control and dietary adherence with a higher proportion of type 2 diabetes patients having good dietary adherence having good glycaemic control compared to those with poor dietary adherence, a finding not observed with BGM, medication and physical activity adherence. This could be related to the non-utilisation of health education messages as well as the non-availability diabetes educators in most of the hospitals in our setting.

This study found that 65.4% of our study participants had good adherence to diet, a finding higher than that obtained in Ethiopia [20, 22] and Brazil, [8, 17] but similar to that reported in Nigeria [18]. The difference in dietary adherence levels can be explained by differences in nutritional habits and use of herbs in the management of type 2 diabetes amongst patients widely available in most African countries.

Having glucometer at home greatly enforces the control of the patients to measure their blood glucose level regularly. In this present study, we also observed that 29.0%, 46.3% and 49.4% had good adherence to BGM, physical activity and proper medication intake respectively. These findings are different from those obtained in Brazil [17], Nigeria [18], Ghana [23] and Ethiopia [22]. A report by Schmitt *et al.* [36] found that irregular measurement of blood glucose amongst diabetic patients was mainly due to a lack of personal glucometers or poor access to laboratories and health facilities. The poor adherence to BGM measurements might be attributed to the fact that less than one-third of the study participants owned a glucometer at home. In addition, variation in physical activity and medication adherence might be due to differences in cultural values, lifestyle, literacy levels and differences in the way diabetic educational messages are disseminated amongst study participants in the different settings. These findings highlight the necessity for more aggressive diabetes education programmes to sensitize patients on the different diabetes self-care practices in order to improve the outcome, quality of life and reduce complications amongst adults living with type 2 diabetes.

Evidence has demonstrated that patients' socio-demographic factors such as gender, age level of education are associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours [37]. Bivariate analysis (unadjusted associations between diabetes self-care behaviours and individual factors) indicated that being 67 years and older (OR 5.3, 95% CI, 1.1 – 10.8) and diabetes duration of more than 5 years (OR=4.6, 95% CI, 1.2 – 13.9) were significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated with adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. This is similar to a report from Thailand [38], which revealed that longer diabetes duration was a positive predictor of diabetes self-care behaviour. The multivariate model revealed that being older than 67 years (OR 4.8, 95% CI, 1.9 – 14.8) was an independent predictor for good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviour in our setting. These findings indicate that special attention be given to younger patients and newly diagnosed adults with type 2 diabetes in order to prevent long term complications and improve outcome of patients. This is can be attributed to the fact that older adults with longer diabetes duration have been exposed to the disease for a longer period resulting in experience in the self-care management practices.

However, educational level, good adherence to BGM (OR=1.1, 95% CI, 0.6 – 2.3), diet adherence (OR=1.2, 95% CI, 0.4 – 1.7), adherence to physical activity of 30 minutes/day (OR=0.8 95% CI, 0.3 – 2.0) and medication adherence (OR=1.2, 95% CI, 0.6 – 2.3) were not significant ($p > 0.05$) associated with good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours. These findings are in contrast to those observed in Jordan [35] where the authors reported that exercise, diet and BGM were significantly associated with adherence to diabetes self-care practices.

The main limitations of this study included the cross-sectional nature of the study cannot be used to establish causality as such findings might not be a true reflection of adherence to self-care practices amongst type 2 diabetes patients in the country. Finally, given that measurement of adherence to the different diabetes self-care behaviours was self-reported, there could have been bias in the reporting as there could have been underreporting given most of the domains of diabetes self-care practices were low.

In spite the limitations of this study, it has provided for the first time data on adherence to four domains (BGM, diet, medication and physical activity) of diabetes self-care behaviours amongst type 2 diabetes patients in the North West Region of Cameroon. Given the association between diabetes self-care behaviours and health outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes, the

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low adherence levels observed for BGM, medication and physical activity amongst the study participants is worrisome. Therefore, there is need for effective strategies in order to improve the diabetes self-care behaviours amongst adult type 2 diabetic patients in the country.

Conclusions

This study amongst T2DM patients in Cameroon has shown that the overall adherence level of the diabetes self-care behaviours amongst adults living with type 2 diabetes is low and being older than 67 years was an independent predictor of good adherence to diabetes self-care behaviours in our setting. Therefore, adults living with T2DM require an integrated approach in the management of T2DM involving treatment as well as health education that will improve on the health and quality of life of the patients. Further studies should explore the challenges encountered by adult type 2 diabetes patients in effectively adhering to the prescribed diabetes self-care behaviours. This data will help to inform targeted intervention as such improve adherence to self-care behaviours.

References

1. International Diabetes Federation, 2021, IDF Diabetes Atlas, 10th edition, Brussels, Belgium: International Diabetes Federation
2. Zheng Y, Ley SH, Hu FB, 2018, Global aetiology and epidemiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus and its complications, *Nat Rev Endocrinol.*, 14(2): 88-98
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nrendo.2017.151>
3. Reed, J, Bain, S, Kanamarlapudi, V, 2021, A review of current trends in type 2 diabetes epidemiology, aetiology, pathogenesis, treatments and future perspectives, *Diabetes, Metabolic, Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*, 4: 3567- 3602.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S319895>
4. World Health Organization. Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. (2006). Guidelines for the prevention, management and care of diabetes mellitus.
<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/119799>
5. Blonde, L, 2005, Current challenges in diabetes management, *Clin Cornerstone*, 7;Suppl 3: S6-17. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1098-3597\(05\)80084-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1098-3597(05)80084-5)
6. American Diabetes Association, 2015, Standards of medical care in diabetes - 2015: Position statement, *Diabetes Care*, 38, (Suppl 1), S1-S93.
7. Shrivastava, SR, Shrivastava, PS, Ramasamy, J, 2013, Role of self-care in the management of diabetes mellitus, *J Diabetes & Metabolic Disorders*, 12 (14): 1-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/2251-6581-12-14>

8. Portela RA, Silva JRS, Nunes FBBF, Lopes MLH, Batista RFL, Silva ACO, 2022, Diabetes mellitus type 2: factors related to adherence to self-care, Rev Bras, Enferm, 75(4): e20210260. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2021-0260>
9. Zhou Y, Liao L, Sun M, He, G, 2013, Self-care practices of Chinese individuals with diabetes, Exp.The.Med, 5(4):1137-1142. <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2013.945>
10. Malanda UL, Welschen LM, Riphagen II, Dekker JM, Nijpels G, Bot SDM, 2012, Self-monitoring of blood glucose in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus who are not using insulin, Cochrane Database Syst Rev 18(1): CD005060. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD005060.pub3>
11. Thomas DE and Elliott EJ, 2010, The use of low-glycaemic index diets in diabetes control, Br J Nutr, 104(6): 797-802. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114510001534>
12. Addisu Y, Eshete A, Hailu E, 2013, Assessment of diabetic patient perception on diabetic disease and self-care practice in Dilla University Referral Hospital, South Ethiopia. J Metabolic Syndr, 3(4): 1-8
13. Chaurasia N, Mishra R, Ling H, Thapa B, Pokhrel A, Kumar S, De, A, 2015 A self-care management awareness study among diabetes mellitus patients in rural Nepal, Am J Public Health Res, 3(5):67-71.
14. Katz ML, Laffel LM, Perrin JM, Kuhlthau K, 2012, Impact of type 1 diabetes mellitus on the family is reduced with the medical home, care coordination, and family-centered care, J Pediatr, 160(5):861-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2011.10.010>
15. Burman J, Bhattacharya, A, Chattopdhyay, AC, Dey, I, Sembiah, S, Negi, R , 2021, Self-care practice and its predictors amongst type 2 diabetes mellitus patients in the outpatient department of a tertiary hospital of Kilkata, Eastern India- A cross-sectional study, J of Fam Med and Prim Care, 10: 1377-82. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe_2070_20
16. Adhikari Baral, I, Baral, S, 2021, Self-care management among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Tanahun, Nepal., Arch Community Med Public Health, 7(1):037-042. <https://doi.org/10.17352/2455-5479.000131>
17. Degefa, G, Wubshet, K, Tesfaye, S, Hirigo, AT, 2020, Predictors of adherence towards specific domains of diabetic self-care among type 2 diabetes patients, Endocrinology and Diabs, 13: 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1179551420981909>
18. Enikuomihin AC, Olamoyegun MA, Ojo OA, Ajani GD, Akinlade TA, Ala OA, 2021, Pattern of self-care practices among type 2 diabetes patients in Southwest, Nigeria, Niger J Clin Pract 24:978-85. <https://doi.org/10.1530/endoabs.86.P228>
19. Gulentie, TM, Yesuf, EM, Yazie, TS, Kefale, B, 2020, Predictors of diabetes self-care practice among patients with type 2 diabetes in public hospitals in Northeastern Ethiopia: A facility-based cross-sectional study, Diab, Metab Syndr and Obesity: Targets and Therapy, 13:3137-3147. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S273682>

20. Gameda, ST and Woldermariam, ZB, 2022, Assessment of self-care practice amongst patients with type II diabetes attending Adama Hospital Medical College, Ethiopia, BMC Endocrine Disorders, 22(132): 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12902-022-01049-9>
21. Diriba DC, Bekuma TT, Bobo FT, 2020, Predictors of self-management practices among diabetic patients attending hospitals in western Oromia, Ethiopia, PLoS ONE, 15(5): e0232524. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0232524>
22. Oluma, A, Mossia, G, Tsegaye, R, Habte, A, Abdissa, E, Predictors of adherence to self-care behaviour among patients with diabetes at public hospitals in West Ethiopia, Diab, Metab Syndr and Obesity: Targets and Therapy, 13: 3277-3288.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S266589>
23. Agidew,E, Wale, MZ, Kerebih, H, Yirsaw, MT, Zewdie, TH, Girma, M, Miskir, A, 2021, Adherence to diabetes self-care management and associated factors among people with diabetes in Gamo Gofa Zone public health hospitals, SAGE Open Medicine, 9:1-7
<https://doi.org/10.1177/20503121211053953>
24. Kassa, RN, Inrahim, IY, Hailemariam, HA, Habte, MH, 2021, Self-care practice and its predictors among adults with diabetes mellitus on follow up at public hospitals of Arsi zone, southeast Ethiopia, BMC Res Notes, 14(102): 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-021-05511-0>
25. Bayable, SD, Misganaw, A, Ashebir, YG, 2022, Self-care practice and its predictors among adult diabetic patients on follow-up at public health care diabetic referral clinics, Debre Markos, Ethiopia, Preventive Medicine Reports, 30(102041): 1-5
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2022.102041>
26. Bongor, Z, Shiferaw, S, Tariku, ES, 2018, Adherence to diabetic self-care practices and its associated factors among patients with type 2 diabetes in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, Patient Preference and Adherence, 12:963-970. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S156043>
27. Mogre, V, Abanga, ZO, Tzelepis, F, Johnson, NA, Paul, C, 2017, Adherence to and factors associated with self-care behaviours in type 2 diabetes patients in Ghana, BMC Endocrine Disorders, 17(20): 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12902-017-0169-3>
28. World Health Organization, 1999, Definition, diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus and its complications, Report of a WHO consultation. Part 1: diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus, WHO/NCD/NCS/99.2, Geneva.
29. Cole TJ, Bellizzi MC, Flegal KM, Dietz WH, 2000, Establishing a standard definition for child overweight and obesity worldwide: international survey, Br Med J, 320(7244):1240-3. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.320.7244.1240>
30. American Diabetes Association, 2018, 'Standards of medical care in diabetes - 2018: Position statement', Diabetes Care, 41, (Suppl 1), S1-S156. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc18-Sint01>

31. Toobert DJ, Hampson SE, Glasgow RE, 2000, The summary of diabetes self-care activities measure: results from 7 studies and a revised scale, *Diabetes Care*, 23:943-50. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diacare.23.7.943>
32. Tang TS, Brown MB, Funnell MM, Anderson RM, 2008, Social support, quality of life, and self-care behaviors among African Americans with type 2 diabetes, *Diabetes Educ*, 34(2):266-76. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0145721708315680>
33. Alhaiti, AH, Senitan, M, Dator, LT, Sankarapandian, C, Baghdadi, NA, Jones, LK, Da Costa, C, Lenon, GB, 2020, Adherence of type 2 diabetic patients to self-care activity: tertiary care setting in Saudi Arabia, *J of Diab Res*, 2020:1- 7 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/4817637>
34. Babazadeh, T, Lofti, Y, Ranjbaran, S, 2021, Predictors of self-care behaviours and glycaemic control among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, *Front. Public Health* 10(1031655): 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.1031655>
35. Almomani MH, Al-Tawalbeh S, 2022, Glycemic Control and Its Relationship with Diabetes Self-Care Behaviors Among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes in Northern Jordan: a cross-sectional study, *Patient Prefer Adherence*, 16: 449 – 465. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S343214>
36. Schmitt A, Gahr A, Hermanns N, Kulzer B, Huber J, Haak T, 2013, The Diabetes self-management questionnaire (DSMQ): Development and evaluation of an instrument to assess diabetes self-care activities associated with glycaemic control. *Health Qual Life Outcomes*; 11(138): 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1477-7525-11-138>
37. Emmanuel OO, Otovwe A, 2015, Patterns of adherence to management among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in South-South Region of Nigeria, *J Soc Health Diabetes*, 3(2):115-119. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2321-0656.152808>
38. Kaehaban S, Hongsranagon P, Havanond P, 2018, Factors influencing self-care behaviors of diabetic patients in diabetes mellitus clinic, Changan Hospital, Roi et Province, Thailand, *J Health Res*, 24(Suppl1): 21-26.

Abbreviations

T2DM	Type 2 diabetes mellitus
IDF	International Diabetes Federation
DM	Diabetes mellitus
CI	Confidence interval
OR	Odds ratio
TM	Traditional medicine
DM	Diabetes mellitus
WHO	World Health Organization
ADA	American Diabetes Association
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance

Data Availability

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The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in this publication.

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Authors' contribution

LLN was responsible for the conception and design of the study, directed data collection and organization, statistical analysis and drafting of the manuscript. ATL contributed to the conception and design of the study, participated in data collection as well as interpretation and drafting of the manuscript. LKN contributed to the conception and design of the study, participated in data collection, analysis of data and interpretation of data as well as drafting of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript for submission.